

Effect of Store Attributes, Past Buying Behaviour and Past Buying Experience

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Abstract:

Background: Apparel retail business is becoming more competitive year by year. Though various factors influence apparel purchase decision of a consumer, store attributes is one of the important factor plays a significant role. Various studies have found that there was a positive relationship between store attributes and buying intention. Besides, past apparel buying behaviour and past apparel buying experience may also play a significant role in the apparel purchase decision. The aim of this study is to study the effect of store attributes on future apparel buying intention and also to study the moderating role of past apparel buying behaviour and past buying experience between store attributes and future buying intention.

Methods: Materials and methods used were a structured questionnaire to collect data from 761 respondents. The collected data was analysed using correlation, regression analysis, and structural equation modelling to study the above stated problem.

Result & Conclusion: The results showed that there were significant positive effects of store attributes, past apparel buying behaviour and past apparel buying experience on future apparel buying intention. It was also found that there was a partial mediating effect of past apparel buying behaviour and past apparel buying experience between store attributes and future buying intention. Recommendations were suggested to apparel retailers in several management practices related to trial rooms, parking, billing, packing and other facilities.

Keywords: apparel retailing, buying intention, past buying behaviour; past buying experience, store attributes.

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1. Introduction

Apparel retailing industry is growing steadily in developing countries like India. Organised retailing format is also growing rapidly at these countries especially in the apparel sector. Though online retailing is increasing at a rapid rate still brick and mortar store plays important role in the retailing business. All these bring a severe competition in the apparel retail business. Various factors influence apparel purchase decision of a consumer. Store attributes may influence consumers' shopping decisions. Many studies have investigated the relationship between store attributes and patronage behaviour and found that the importance of different attributes affected consumer's retail store selection. Researchers have sought to identify customers' motivation for shopping and the store attributes are the most important to various segments of shoppers.

Earlier studies argued that store image attributes developed earlier were important but not sufficient enough to understand store performance and customer behavior [1]. Studies on the customer perceptions for store attributes in unorganized retail stores in India found that there was a positive relationship between customer perceptions and store attributes [2]. The store attributes might be the basic satisfying factor and there was a possibility that unavailability of store attributes might lead to customer

dissatisfaction [3]. Scholars attempted to address issues related to store attributes and their relevance in the store selection process in their study of customer perceptions of store attributes towards organized retail outlets in India [4].

Few scholars stated that understanding patronage behaviour was one of the keys to success for today's retailers and it was necessary that stores which retail attributes are important to shoppers so that the appropriate retail strategies can be developed [5]. Some studies examined the influence of retail attributes on retail format preference and the study found that there was a significant relation between the retail format preference and retail attribute importance [6]. Retail store is the place where consumers actually make the final purchase decision. Even though most of the consumers have already made some purchase decision in their mind before entering the store, still the final purchase decision may be changed during the in-store purchase process. Apparel retail store attributes play important role in apparel purchase decision of the consumers. The aim of this study is to study the effect of retail store attributes on future apparel buying intention, effect of past buying behaviour and past buying experience on future apparel buying intention and moderating effect of past apparel buying behaviour and past apparel buying experience between store attributes and future apparel buying intention.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Store Attributes

Store attributes are the characteristics, features or elements that one store has. This includes the services & facilities

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available and provided in the store, the promotional efforts made by the store with respect to different types of promotions, the business ethics that is being adapted by the store and the social responsibility of the store towards the society.

Many studies have discussed the impact of store atmospherics and store lay out on consumer buying patterns and identified seven factors store atmospherics, store layout & design, customer service, visual communication, promotions, problems solving & policy and reliability [1]. Few scholars included store image, product assortments, discount, retailer attributes and product availability as store attribute variables in their study of customer perceptions for store attributes in unorganized retail stores in India [2]. Some studies identified five factors of store attributes, store environment & services, style & quality of apparel, price & sales management, advertising management and merchandise management in her study [3]. Few more studies initially identified eleven store attribute variables based on theoretical judgment and using factor analysis finally arrived three factors, convenience & merchandise mix, store atmospherics and services [4].

A study referred to one of the several variables, which influenced apparel purchase behaviour was the nature of retail environment and regional shopping malls were popular place due to their comfortable surroundings and pleasant atmosphere [7]. A survey on recreational shoppers in urban settings found that environmental factors such as store variety, street decoration, and store decor were important determinants of activity levels. Several scholars studied the factors influencing the purchase decision by using the factors like product attributes, price attributes, place attributes and promotion attributes [8].

2.1.1 Services and facilities

Services and facilities include parking space, store décor, trial room, card services like credit card acceptance, membership card availability etc., alteration services, credit payment options, lighting etc. The physical environment of stores including elements such as layout, interior architecture and decor, lighting, music, aromas, and cleanliness have been found to influence consumers' emotional states [9, 10 & 11]. Few researchers argued that consumers would select stores that include positive moods and avoid those that create negative ones [12]. Apparel retail brands Levis and Allen Solly started the concept of providing jeans, formal suits and blazers on a monthly instalment basis in Indian market [13, 14].

2.1.2 Promotion

Promotion is a component in the marketing mixes which is a kind of communication with consumers. Promotion includes the use of advertising, sales promotion, personal selling and publicity. It greatly affects consumers' image, beliefs and attitude towards products and brands and in turn influence their purchase behaviour [15]. Advertisement could help establishing ideas or perceptions in the consumers' mind and differentiating the store against other stores. Thus good advertisements could create store loyalty [16]. Some authors

in their study found that there was strong significant relationship between the presence of promotional flyers in the store and purchase quantities [17].

2.1.3 Business ethics and social responsibility

Corporate Social Responsibility is the social responsibility of business encompasses the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary expectations that society has of organisations at a given point in time [18]. CSP is described as a multidimensional construct comprising initiatives undertaken by a company in to four broad domains: the natural environment, the treatment of employees, workplace diversity, customers, product and other issues [18].

Now a day there is a growing concern about the way in which businesses are performed. Environmentalist and other non-government organisations have been actively spreading awareness about the gradual depletion of the earth's resources. Consumers were looking for detailed information on the social and environmental impacts of the business activities of the company from whom they purchase their products [19]. Some studies found that consumer purchase decisions were affected by the retail store business ethics but limited to certain factors like price, quality and distance [20]. Few scholars studied the initial understanding of female consumers' decision to purchase from socially responsible apparel business and found that product-specific attitudes were related to intentions to purchase from socially responsible apparel businesses [21]. In some studies it was found that consumers had favourable attitude towards the stores which involved in the CSR activities, which was beneficial to local society [22].

2.2 Past Buying Behaviour

Consumer buying behavior is how individuals, groups and organizations to select, purchase, use and disposal of products, services, ideas or experience to meet the consumers' demand. Buying behavior is the decision processes and acts people involved in buying and using products which includes social and mental process [23].

Past buying behaviour means the buying behaviour of the consumers towards a particular product in the recent past. Many researchers have discussed about past buying behaviour while studying consumer buying behaviour [24-27].

2.3 Past Buying Experience

The concept of customer experience has been discussed by many authors and it has been conceptualized early that consumption has experiential effects [29] and the customer experience is the driver of brand equity [29]. It was proposed that customer experience was an individual interpretation of the service process and its interactions or touch-points, that influence customers' feelings [30]. Some studies proposed customer experience as the outcome of customers' interactions with the firm, including the interaction with the staff, self-service technologies, and the service environment [31]. Few scholars identified the critical importance customer experience improvement programmes and the

ways in which customers could be directly engaged in the design and improvement process [32].

Past buying experience refers to the experience of the consumers that they had experienced during their previous purchases of a particular product. Various studies included this factor in their studies on consumer buying behaviour [33-36].

2.4 Future Buying Intention

Various researches indicated purchase intentions were a positive consequence of emotional value, in relation to both store patronage and consumers' need for uniqueness and status consumption. Consumer purchase intention is considered as a subjective inclination toward a store and can be an important index to predict consumer behaviour. Few studies found that there was a high degree of correlation with brand responses and purchase intentions [37] and contended that buying intention could be categorised in to planned buying, unplanned buying and partially planned buying [38].

2.5 Methods

2.5.1 Research Model and Hypotheses

The research framework is depicted in Figure1. And the hypotheses statement are as follows:

Hypothesis 1: The store attributes are positively related to past apparel buying behaviour.

Hypothesis 2: The store attributes are positively related to past apparel buying experience.

Hypothesis 3: The store attributes are positively related to future apparel buying intention.

Hypothesis 4: Past buying behaviour is positively related to past apparel buying experience.

Hypothesis 5: Past buying behaviour is positively related to future apparel buying intention.

Hypothesis 6: Past buying experience is positively related to future apparel buying intention.

2.5.2 Sampling Technique

Non- random and convenience sampling method was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in 10 corporation cities in the state of Tamil Nadu, India. They are Chennai, Vellore, Salem, Erode, Tirupur, Coimbatore, Trichy, Madurai, Tirunelveli and Tuticorin. The sample size of this study was 761. From each city 80 sample respondents were selected and a total of 800 questionnaires were collected. Out of 800 questionnaires, 39 questionnaires were incomplete and only 761 questionnaires can be usable. So, the sample size was arrived to 761.

2.5.3 Measures

Three attributes viz. service and facilities, promotion, and business ethics & social responsibility were used for store attributes. These 3 attributes containing 20 items were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). 11 items were used to measure the past apparel buying behaviour and future apparel buying intentions. 3 attributes (6 items) were used to measure the past buying experience. A five point Likert scale was used to measure the ratings (except for future apparel buying intention), from Strongly Agree was given a rating of 5 to Strongly Disagree was given a rating of 1. For future apparel buying intention, it was Most Likely (5) to Most Unlikely(1).

3. Results

3.1 Demographic Descriptive

The demographic descriptive analysis shows that out of 761 respondents, 56.37% of respondents were female, 72.54% of respondents were belong to age group upto 25 years, 53.09% of respondents had UG education, 55.06% of respondents were students, 75.56% of respondents were married, and 35.48% and 33.51% of respondents had spent on apparel between Rs. 2000 – 4000 and Above Rs. 4000 respectively.

3.2 Reliability Statistics

Table 1 shows the reliability statistics and it is inferred that the Cronbach's α for factors, store attributes with 20 items

Source: Developed by author

Figure 1 - Research Model

was .847 (.854), past buying behaviour with 11 items was .816 (.816), past buying experience with 6 items was .720 (.725) and future buying behaviour with 11 items was .807 (.808).

Table 1 - Reliability statistics

S. No	Variables	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Standardized Items
1	Store Attributes	20	.847	.854
2	Past buying behaviour	11	.816	.816
3	Past buying experience	6	.720	.725
4	Future buying behaviour	11	.807	.808

Source: Primary Data

According to Guileford (1965), when Cronbach's α is greater than 0.7, it shows that the questionnaire has a relatively high internal reliability. The results of the study show that Cronbach's α in all constructs were higher than 0.7. It indicates that the reliability of the questionnaire is acceptable.

3.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to assess the validity of the measures. According to Hair et al (1998) item loading over .50 is very important significance, over .40 is important significance and over .30 is the minimum level of practical significance [40]. The factor loadings for the items were services & facilities (.805), promotion (.725) and business ethics & social responsibility (.758). All the items under store attributes factor have item loadings over 0.5. The composite reliability of the items is 0.807 and the average variance expected (AVE) is 0.582 or 58.2%. So all the items under store attribute factor were confirmed.

3.4 Correlation Analysis

Table 2 presents correlations among the store attributes, past buying behaviour, past buying experience and future buying intention. Many significant relationships were found among variables related to the store attributes, past buying behaviour, past buying experience and future buying intention.

Table 2 - Correlation analysis

S. No	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Services & Facilities	1					
2	Promotion	.385**	1				
3	Ethics	.427**	.308**	1			
4	Past buying behaviour	.115**	.242**	.161**	1		
5	Past buy experience	.418**	.257**	.275**	.264**	1	
6	Future buying intention	.170**	.286**	.173**	.646**	.226**	1

Source: Primary Data; ** Pearson Correlation is significant at the $p < 0.01$ level (2-tailed).

The variable 'service and facilities' had significant positive relationship at 1% level among variables promotion ($r = .385, p < .01$), ethics ($r = .427, p < .01$), past buying behaviour ($r = .115, p < .01$), past buying experience ($r = .418, p < .01$) and future buying behaviour ($r = .170, p < .01$).

The variable 'promotion' had significant positive relationship at 1% level among variables ethics ($r = .308, p < .01$), past buying behaviour ($r = .242, p < .01$), past buying experience ($r = .257, p < .01$) and future buying behaviour ($r = .286, p < .01$). The variable 'business ethics & social responsibility' had significant positive relationship at 1% level among variables past buying behaviour ($r = .161, p < .01$), past buying experience ($r = .275, p < .01$) and future buying behaviour ($r = .173, p < .01$). Most of the expected correlations were found among the research variables. As predicted, all the store attributes viz. services and facilities, promotion and ethics have significant positive correlation among past buying behaviour, past buying experience and future buying behaviour.

3.5 Simple Regression Analysis

Table 3 presents the results of the simple linear regression analysis which shows that the store attributes had a significant effect on - past buying behaviour ($\beta = .234, p < .05$); past buying experience ($\beta = .400, p < .05$), and future buying behaviour ($\beta = .358, p < .05$); Also past buying behaviour had a significant effect on - past buying experience ($\beta = .264, p < .05$) and future buying behaviour ($\beta = .646, p < .05$). Also past buying experience had a significant effect on future buying behaviour ($\beta = .226, p < .05$). This gives support for hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, and H6.

Table 3 - Simple regression

S. No	Variables	B	β	Sig.
1	Store Attribute - Past buying behaviour	.316	.234	.000
2	Store Attribute - Past buying experience	.437	.400	.000
3	Store Attribute - Future buying behaviour	.358	.280	.000
4	Past buying behaviour - Past buying experience	.214	.264	.000
5	Past buying behaviour - Future buying behaviour	.613	.646	.000
6	Past buying experience - Future buying behaviour	.265	.226	.000

Source: Primary data

3.6 Structural Equation Modelling

3.6.1 Measurement model

Table 4 shows the results of measurement model. The loading values for store attributes items were services & facilities (1.118), promotion (.863) and business ethics & social responsibility (.762). the loading values for past

buying experience were apparel satisfaction (.697), store satisfaction (.725) and past experience (.646). All the loading values were significant at $p < .05$.

Table 4 - Measurement model

S. No.	Factors	Items	Loading	Std. Error	T-statistics
1	Store attributes	Service & Facilities	1.118	0.188	5.9344
		Promotion	0.863	0.198	4.3493
		Ethics	0.762	0.133	5.6939
2	Past buying experience	Apparel satisfaction	0.697	0.041	16.8408
		Store satisfaction	1.101	0.038	28.7755
		Past experience	0.646	0.040	16.1517

Source: Primary data

3.6.2 Structural Equation Model

The structural equation model was tested in order to examine the hypothesized relationship among latent variables. The results are shown in table 5 and figure 2.

Table 5 - Structural equation model

Path	Estimate coefficients	S.E error	T-Statistic	Sig.
Store attributes → Past buying behaviour	0.049	0.024	2.041*	Significant
Store attributes → Past buying experience	0.122	0.045	2.710**	Significant
Store attributes → Future buying behaviour	0.090	0.033	2.682**	Significant
Past buying behavior → Past buying experience	0.059	0.028	2.107*	Significant
Past buying behavior → Future buying behaviour	0.049	0.023	2.130*	Significant
Past buying experience → Future buying behaviour	0.158	0.054	2.915**	Significant
R ² value				
Past buying behaviour	0.400			
Past buying experience	0.268			
Future buying behaviour	0.309			

Source: Primary data

Figure 2 illustrates the structural model showing significant and insignificant paths using unstandardized coefficients. Among factors, the path coefficients for store attributes factors, between store attributes and past buying behaviour ($\gamma = .049$, $t = 2.041$, $p < .05$), store attributes and past buying experience ($\gamma = .122$, $t = 2.710$, $p < .01$), store attributes and future buying behaviour ($\gamma = .090$, $t = 2.682$, $p < .01$), were

positive and significant. This result provides support for hypotheses H1, H2, and H3.

The path coefficients for past buying behaviour factor, between past buying behaviour and past buying experience ($\gamma = .059$, $t = 2.107$, $p < .05$), past buying behaviour and future buying behaviour ($\gamma = .049$, $t = 2.130$, $p < .01$), were positive and significant. So the hypotheses H4 and H5 were supported. The path coefficients for past buying experience factor and future buying intention ($\gamma = .158$, $t = 2.915$, $p < .01$), were positive and significant. So, the hypothesis H6 was supported. The R² values for the factors past buying behaviour is 0.4, past buying experience is 0.268, and the future buying intention is 0.309. The overall chi-square value is 30711.130 df. 5886, $p < .001$ the RMSEA (multi R²) = 0.1

Figure 2 - Structural Equation Model

4. Discussion

When we see the results of store attributes on past buying behaviour in all the analyses i.e. correlation, regression and SEM, it showed that there was a positive relationship of store attributes on past buying behaviour. It means that the consumers when purchased apparel in the previous instances given considerable importance to the store attributes. When we the results of store attributes on past buying experience, in all the analyses showed that there were positive effects of store attributes on past buying experience. This means that the consumers had considerable good buying experiences in their previous apparel purchases. The results of store attributes on future buying intention, in all the analyses showed that there were positive effects of store attributes on future. This means that consumers will give significant importance to the store attributes while purchase apparel in the future. In the results of SEM model, the path coefficient of the store attributes on past buying experience and path coefficient of past buying experience had higher significant effect than the other paths. This shows that the store attributes play important role in providing better buying experience and past buying experience provides the better chances of consumer buying apparel in the future.

Consumers get most of the buying experience mainly inside the retail store while making the purchase. This buying experience can be enhanced through various store attributes. The first buying experience for the customers, who visit the apparel store, starts in the parking space. Now most of the customers come in personal vehicles for purchase. So they

always look for enough and comfortable parking space. Searching for parking space always irritates the customer. Good parking space gives good initial buying experience to the customers. The parking space may be based on coupon system where the customer will pay initially the parking fee and that can be exchanged with the bill while customer making purchase in that store.

In most of the apparel stores, the trial rooms are small and congested. Trial rooms with enough space and facilities like table, hangers, security while changing the dress etc. Digital mirror in the trial rooms is a good option. With digital mirror placed in trial rooms, consumers no need to physically wear the garment and see. They can try them virtually in the digital mirror. One of the main reasons a customer visits an apparel store is the volume of varieties or assortment available in the store. So, making available of more number of varieties and good collections is important one. The store can provide free wi-fi connection in the store. It can be used by consumers for getting information about the products immediately in their smart mobile phones, which would be useful for them in their purchase decision. Store can install digital kiosks which shows the apparel collection in the store so that customers can quickly look through the collections and can make purchase decision easily. This saves time and energy for both the consumer and retailer.

In big multi-branded apparel retail stores billing and delivery takes more time than in other apparel retail formats. Faster billing and delivery will improve the buying experience. There is an opportunity to provide improved buying experience while packing the consumers' purchased apparel before delivering it to customers. The packing bag may be of eco friendly material and can have both the functional and fashionable features. For example, the packing bag may be made of 'plant grow bag material' which is made of BPA (Bisphenol A) free polypropylene sheet or fabric. This fabric or sheet allows plant roots to breathe and ensures good drainage. So the customers can use this bag as plant grow bag to grow plants or vegetables in their home. Consumer friendly product return policies may be implemented. One of the important strategies is making the customers delight. Delighting the customers with freebies according to seasons, or functions – umbrellas, cloth bags, pouches, handkerchiefs, etc. In a big multi branded apparel retail stores, where people spend considerable time for apparel purchase, refreshment outlets or kiosks can be installed. These outlets can provide refreshment items at cheaper prices i.e. with very less

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margins. This strategy would be very helpful in providing improved buying experience, in addition, also this would give additional income or it would reduce the operating cost of the store.

5. Conclusion

The present research work has led the researcher study effect of store attributes, past apparel buying behaviour and past apparel buying experience on future apparel buying intention. The outcome of this research would provide the apparel retailers an insight into planning retail strategies with respect to retail store attributes to provide enhanced buying experience to the customers, which in turn would improve the buying intention of the customers to purchase in that particular store. These would further act as guidelines for the retailing strategies such as product differentiation, quality enhancement, value for money, and promotional mix.

5.1 Future Scope and Limitations

The finding of this study indicates that the proposed model worked well for the apparel retailing. The proposed model can be used to test the buying behaviour for other retail products. Such future studies on testing the model in various retail products may increase the robustness of the model explaining consumer behaviour in various retail environments. In this study the focus is given on the apparel buying behaviour in the retail store, in future this model can be tested for apparel buying behaviour in online and other retail formats. The ethnicity of the consumers may have substantial impact on the apparel buying behaviour, so in future this model may be tested toward different ethnicities.

The research has a number of limitations that must be acknowledged. Mainly this study was conducted with limited number of respondents and to test the proposed apparel buying intention model, this study used a convenience sample of customers who were willing to respond, therefore the findings cannot be generalized universally. This study only examines the effect of store attributes, past apparel buying behaviour and past apparel buying experience on future apparel buying intention. Also, there may be some other factors that may have influence on consumers' future apparel buying intention which are not included in this study. For instance, the situational factors for out-of-stock merchandise, time pressure, and consumer subjective knowledge in clothing may influence consumers' purchase behaviour.

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